

A Zero-Touch and NFV-Based Full-Mesh VPNaaS Solution - Demo

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Abstract—NFV has risen to be a solution to abstract Network Functions from the hardware, providing numerous advantages to Network Operators. However, many challenges have appeared with the evolution of NFV. An example are the inter-domain scenarios where services are spanned across multiple independent domains. Using VPNs to interconnect all domains can attenuate the difficulties imposed by such scenarios. In this paper, we present a NFV-based solution for deploying full-mesh VPNs to interconnect different administrative domains, without manual intervention.

Index Terms—NFV, 5G, VPNaaS, Zero-touch, SFC

I. INTRODUCTION

To accomplish the separation of Network Functions (NFs) from the hardware they operate on, Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) exploits virtualization methods [1]. This makes it feasible to abstract NFs from the hardware where they are deployed, facilitating their deployment on Commercial-Of-The-Shelf (COTS) servers. Additionally, these Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs) are simple to modify to meet the customer's needs, contributing to their increased flexibility, performance, and reliability [2].

The benefits of NFV are emphasized further in cases where VNFs are linked through Service Function Chains (SFCs), which deliver complex network services. SFCs enable the placement of VNFs under a specific topology, with traffic being directed between the VNFs based on a pre-determined rule set [3].

Recently, inter-domain scenarios have become increasingly attractive in NFV as they enable the spanning of services over multiple independent domains, expanding the service's coverage area. In these, an SFC may also be spread across several domains, with its various VNFs placed across them. This enables leveraging the multiple domains' resources to deliver further functions to end-users [3]. However, establishing inter-domain SFCs is a complex procedure due to the extensive negotiations between domains immediately before deploying the SFC's VNFs.

One way to solve the abovementioned issues is using Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) to interconnect all domains where an inter-domain SFC is to be installed. The communication between VNFs hosted in various domains

is confidential due to VPNs's traffic isolation and encryption capabilities. Given the present-day security challenges, this is extremely desired. The adoption of Virtual Private Network-as-a-Services (VPNaaSs) techniques may also make it easier to deploy inter-domain VPN tunnels [4]. The VPN tunnels can be established in advance of deploying the SFC's VNFs. This ensures that the underlying networks have inter-domain connectivity before the VNFs are activated in the different domains.

This paper demonstrates our fully-fledged solution for deploying full-mesh VPNs to interconnect different administrative domains. Our solution is NFV-based, and can be installed without human intervention. The VPN tunnels are established using Wireguard¹. Once the tunnels are deployed and established, Operators may rely entirely on them to ensure inter-domain communication, as in use cases requiring distributed SFCs. This paper is organized as follows. Section II showcases our work proposal and the architecture and implementation of the developed system. Furthermore, section III addresses the demonstration proposed, being segmented into 3 subsections: (i) the scenario of the demonstration, (ii) the steps followed in the demonstration, and (iii) validation of the inter-connectivity. Finally, we present our conclusions in Section IV.

II. AN INTER-DOMAIN MESH VPN AS A SERVICE

A. Work Proposal

Our main goal is to deliver a system capable of providing inter-domain SFCs without human intervention. This system should also provide the capabilities required to enable connectivity between the SFCs that span the independent domains. To address this, we used NetOr [5]. NetOr is an Operations Support System (OSS) system that sits on top of operators' Fifth Generation (5G) infrastructures, providing a platform for vertical service orchestration. NetOr also handles inter-domain scenarios by coordinating the NFV Orchestrators (NFVOs) that reside in the various domains. Furthermore, this system supports run-time operations on the Vertical Services (day-1 and day-2). These features make it an appropriate orchestrator for deploying and configuring our VPNaaS strategy.

¹<https://www.wireguard.com>

Besides this, we aim to offer the utilities required to create an inter-domain connection. By exploiting the features of the previously stated system, these tools will operate on top of it. Additionally, the inter-domain connecting procedure must be as resilient as possible. As a result, it cannot depend on a central module to operate. Having this in mind, we implemented a full-mesh VPN as our VPNaaS solution. A full-mesh VPN offers more throughput and resilience than a non-full-mesh VPN and a hub-and-spoke VPN [4]. Due to its high throughput, straightforward configuration, and lightweight, the Wireguard VPN was employed to provide the VPN tunnels [4] [6].

Our third and final goal is for the VPN tunnels to be automatically configured, creating a completely zero-touch VPNaaS. We can accomplish this by having a central entity forwarding all necessary information. Thus, we chose to employ a central entity that provides Service Discovery (SD), a fundamental premise of microservice architectures. After careful evaluation we opted for Domain Name System (DNS)-based SD [7], the Wireguard VPN nodes may store their keys and all necessary information in the DNS Server. As a result, the remaining Wireguard VPN nodes may access this data and continuously retrieve data from the DNS server. Section II-B further details how we achieved this work proposal.

B. Architecture and Implementation

This section presents our VPNaaS solution’s architecture. We start by discussing the architectural improvements we made to NetOr before moving on to the design of the VPNaaS solution itself.

NetOr was built using a micro-services approach to promote flexibility and scalability while decreasing module coupling. Such characteristics facilitate the introduction of new services or functionalities, without having to update the whole system. Thus, we benefited from this to add a *DNS Server* to NetOr, using PowerDNS². These updates to NetOr’s architecture are showcased in figure 1.

When a Vertical Service instantiation request is made, NetOr’s *Coordinator* component creates a zone on the DNS Server for that particular service. Additionally, this component injects instantiation parameters into the initial request. The cipher key, one of the parameters that are injected, is unique to the particular Vertical Service and will be used by the Vertical Service’s VNFs to publish sensitive data in the *DNS Server*. The *Coordinator* will, after that, instruct the *Domain* component to send the extended instantiation requests to the NFVO present in the domains desired to be linked. We adjusted our VPNaaS solution’s implementation to the NFVOs we intended to exploit, which were Open Source MANOs (OSMs). When the instantiation requests arrive at the NFVOs, they deploy the VPN nodes via VNFs enclosed in an Network Service (NS). These will then be configured via Juju³, OSMs’s

²<https://www.powerdns.com/>

³<https://juju.is>

Fig. 1: NetOr’s Updated Architecture

VNF Manager (VNFM). The Juju controllers provided by OSM instantiate Juju Charms that are responsible for day-1 operations. Such operations include (i) installing Wireguard in the VPN nodes, (ii) storing the VPN node’s information in NetOr’s DNS Server, and (iii) gathering all the information required to configure the full-mesh network between all VPN nodes.

Once the VPN nodes have been deployed and all dependencies have been installed, Wireguard’s configuration may begin. During this phase, a private and a public key are created. Wireguard will use these to encrypt the network traffic that will be routed through the VPN tunnels. At this point, the Wireguard service is started, but no tunnels between the VPN nodes are established. To achieve this, the VPN nodes must share (i) their location, (ii) their public key, and (iii) details about the networks that must be accessible through the tunnels with all nodes that should be part of the mesh VPN. Hence, each node will register its information in the DNS Server provided by NetOr, using the cipher key provided. It is worth recalling that the node information exchange complies with the RFC 6763 [7].

After completing their registration, the nodes must continue inquiring NetOr’s DNS Server for other operational nodes. When a new VPN node is discovered, the procedure for establishing a VPN tunnel may begin. However, as we are using Wireguard to provide the tunnels, only an update to the node’s configuration file to include the other nodes’ information is required. Upon completing this update, the Wireguard Service is restarted. The nodes are then prepared to function as a gateway to the networks housed in the other domains. The end architecture of our approach is represented in Figure 2.

After configuring all desired VPN tunnels, new nodes

Fig. 2: Final Solution's Architecture

can still be included in the mesh VPN through day-2 operations. Such capability is based on the continuous probing from the VPN nodes to NetOr's DNS Server to find new nodes to join the mesh VPN. Other day-2 operations are also supported to configure the VPN tunnels. Despite being manually triggered, such operations furnish a more refined management of the tunnels. These operations include (i) obtaining detailed information on the VPN nodes, such as their IPs, resources, etc., (ii) updating the routing of the VPN nodes, (iii) listing all VPN tunnels available to a VPN node, (iv) update the networks that should be exposed by a VPN node, (v) manage the VPN tunnels' bandwidth, and (vi) remove nodes from the mesh VPN.

III. DEMONSTRATION

The demonstration presented in this paper addresses various relevant aspects of the VPNaaS proposed solution. We will showcase the deployment of our VPNaaS solution amongst different administrative domains. Through such deployment it will be possible to observe that the VPN tunnels are established without human intervention. Furthermore, we will also showcase the connectivity provided by the VPN tunnels, by sending network packets between different domains, through the VPN tunnels.

A. Demonstration Scenario

The scenario of our demonstration is composed of three independent domains: (i) the Telecommunications Institute in Portugal, (ii) the University of Múrcia in Spain, and (iii) the University of Patras in Greece. The VPNaaS orchestration process is delegated to NetOr. As a result, a mesh VPN is established between all domains.

B. Demonstration Steps

Showcasing the automation and orchestration of a full-mesh VPN is the main goal of this demonstration. To that end, the demonstration includes the following steps:

- Instantiate the VPNaaS solution through NetOr;
- Showcase in each domain's NFVO the instantiation of the VPN nodes;
- Verify the publishing of the nodes' information to the DNS Server without manual intervention;
- Confirm the tunnels have been established;
- Validate the connectivity between the different domains, provided by the VPN tunnels.

C. Inter-connectivity Validation

The validation of the interconnectivity between all domains relies on the *ping* and *iPerf3* tools. Upon successful execution of *ping* command, we can assume that there is connectivity from one domain to another. Furthermore, through *iPerf3* we shall be able to showcase the bandwidth provided by each VPN tunnel.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This demo paper demonstrates our zero-touch NFV-based full-mesh VPNaaS solution. Our approach simplifies the deployment and configuration of inter-domain SFCs through the orchestration of a full-mesh VPN without prior negotiation between the domains involved. Despite the positive results achieved with our VPNaaS solution, our work is not completed. For future work, we intend to tackle operational issues with our solution's employment. For example, dealing with VPN tunnels becoming nonoperational, affecting the mesh network. To handle this issue, we will provide monitoring capabilities to the VPN nodes, as it is possible to detect when a tunnel is offline and take the required actions to re-establish it.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the European Horizon 2020 Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under Grant 101016448 (5GASP).

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